
**A STUDY OF INFORMATION NEED AND INFORMATION
SEEKING BEHAVIOR OF STUDENTS OF A.Y.K.K'S ARTS
MAHILA COLLEGE, DHULE (MS)**

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.7205205

Abstract:

Adequate knowledge about the information needs and behavior of users is essential for developing library collections, services and facilities to effectively meet their information needs. This study was conducted by A.Y.K.K's Arts Mahila College, Dhule (MS). It was conducted to determine the information seeking behavior and library use of graduate level students in an applied. The overall objective of this study was to determine their information needs and their awareness of library services available to them. A survey method was used for the study undertaken. The study collected data on students' information needs. Data was collected from 80 out of 100 students through a structured questionnaire. In the said questionnaire, of use of library, average time of use, purpose of visit, use of reading material, information search, purpose of search and difficulties faced while searching information in library etc. Questions are asked.

Keyword: - Information, Information use, Information Need, Information Seeking Behavior, Graduate Students.

Introduction:

Library and information science research is an important task of addressing information-related behavior including information needs, information seeking and use of information resources.^{1,2} Today information plays a very important role in human life and is considered as a basic resource. It also affects your personal and professional life. Information is very important to every element of today's information society or human being as it is needed by everyone to make decisions and in their daily activities like any other natural resource. The process of acquiring, using and implementing information is called information seeking behavior. It is

more important for academicians, researchers and students as they need relevant and up-to-date information for their research needs. Information seeking behavior is a broad term that includes actions taken by individuals or groups to demonstrate their need for information, information seeking, examining and selecting information to satisfy their needs or information needs. Information seeking as described by Wilson is a term that refers to how individuals seek, evaluate, select and use information.³ An assessment of information seeking behavior of a graduate student is critical to accessing and using information resources to meet essential information needs.

Literature Review:

Information seeking behavior is one of the most widely researched topics in library and information science, and the literature is generally scattered across disciplines, so it is difficult to conduct a comprehensive review of all studies. But while number of studies have been done on 'Information Seeking Behavior', only a few have attempted a proportionate study.

Das, A.K. (2014)4

A survey was conducted at Bengal Institute of Technology and Management, Bolpur to explore the information demand and searching habits of students in the digital age. This study investigates the use of information technology by students to search for information in this digital age. The study recommends awareness programs for students, guidance on web searching and information seeking skills. Learning Resource Centers should arrange orientation programs, computer enhancement, internet speed and availability of e-resources to meet the needs of students.

Ravichandran et al (2013)5

The study was conducted among Engineering and Arts and Science students studying at undergraduate and postgraduate levels in various colleges in Chennai. The topic was the light on the purposes of searching for information on the Internet and the comparison between the respondents about the use of search engines and information resources. The study revealed that majority of the respondents are using the internet to search for information to prepare for their exams. Respondents belong to Arts and Science stream they use Google search engine to find information on internet. The Internet is widely used to collect information related to the academic performance of

Engineering students when compared to Arts and Science students.

Bhatia and Rao (2011)6

Information sought on behavior of students in Devasamaj College, Chandigarh. The purpose of the study is to find out the use of information technology by college students to obtain information and how they access e-resources. A questionnaire was randomly distributed to 100 students, who visited the library with a response rate of 64%. It was found that less than 50% of the respondents were not aware of e-resources, with users using search engines as a major source for accessing e-resources for their information needs and for updating their knowledge on topics of interest. The study suggested awareness programs for students and provided training in web search and retrieval skills.

Shweta (2010)7

Investigated the information seeking behavior of library students of an autonomous college in Mangalore city. Lack of time, non-availability of all information were seen to be the problems faced by the students while getting information. It was also found that apart from library collection, user's access information through personal collections and colleagues. The study suggested that the library should acquire more number of current periodicals for up-to-date library and inform the students about it.

A.Y.K.K's Arts Mahila College, Dhule - An Introduction:

Abhay Yuva Kalyan Kendra's Arts Mahila College, Dhule was established on 17th June 1989. Initially this college was functioning under Pune University, Pune. On August 15, 1990, North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon was separated from Pune University and the said college is

now affiliated and functioning under the Kavyitri Bahinabai Chaudhary North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon. Only Arts department is functioning in the college and only degree education is available. The number of students is around 200. The college has been certified by NAAC twice so far. Soon the college will face NAAC for the third time. The college has a library and a separate reading room is available for students and faculty.

Conceptual Definition:

- Information: - According to J.H. Shera, “Information is the fact that is the impulse that we experience through our senses. Information may be a single fact or a whole group of facts but is still a unit; It is a single thought”.⁸
- Information Need: - The concept of information needs is the result of the combination of two terms 'information' and 'need'. The concept of information needs was developed by the American information scientist Robert S. Taylor presented in his article “The Process of Asking Questions” published in American Documentation.⁹
- Information Seeking Behavior: - According to Krikelas, “Information seeking begins when one perceives that the current state of knowledge is less than what is needed to tackle some problem. The process ends when understanding no longer exists”¹⁰

Objectives of the Study:

Studying students' information seeking behavior will enable libraries and academic librarians to provide standardized services that will improve the academic performance of their students. This study sought to establish ways to improve students' information seeking behavior. To achieve this goal, the study has set the following objectives:

- To find sources of information known to graduate students;
- Exploring the information needs of graduate students;
- Determining the information demand and use of graduate students;
- To establish the problems faced by graduate students in information.

Procedure:

The survey was limited to the students of Abhay Yuva Kalyan Kendra's Arts Mahila College, Dhule. A questionnaire survey was conducted to collect information regarding library use, purpose of use, satisfaction level of students. A total of 100 questionnaires were distributed to the students and 80 of them were received, giving an overall response rate of 80%. The information collected from the students through the questionnaire was analyzed using simple percentage technique.

Use of College Library: - How frequently used is the college library? A question was asked in this regard. 80 students responded to it.

Table no. 1: Use of College Library

S.N.	Frequency of College Library Use	Respondents	%
1.	Daily	30	37.50
2.	Once a Day	12	15.00
3.	Once a week	15	18.75
4.	Once in a fortnight	10	12.50
5.	Once a month	08	10.00
6.	As and when required	05	6.25
	Total	80	100

Table no. 1, According to when asked about how the respondents use the college library, 37.50% of the total respondents visit the library daily, 18.75%

once a week, 15% once a day, 12.50% once in a fortnight, 10% once a month and 6.25% of the respondents sometimes visit the library as required.

Table no. 2: Average time spent using the library

S.N.	Frequency of College Library Use	Respondents	%
1.	Half to One hour	39	48.75
2.	One to two hour	17	21.25
3.	Two to three hour	13	16.25
4.	More than three hour	11	13.75
Total		80	100

Table no. 2, According to when asked about the average time the respondents use the college library, 48.75% of the total respondents visit the

library for half an hour to one hour, 21.25% one to two hours, 16.25% two to three hours, 13.75% % visit the library for more than three hours.

Table no. 3: Purpose of visiting the library

S.N.	Purpose of Visiting Library	Respondents	%
1.	To collect information	29	36.25
2.	for information in reference books	37	46.25
3.	for loan of books	68	85.00
4.	To refer to journals/periodicals	25	31.25
5.	prepare research paper	03	3.75
6.	refer theses	02	2.50
7.	to study	55	68.75
8.	for reading newspaper	62	77.50

Table no. 3, According to when respondents were asked about the purpose of visiting the college library, 85% of the total respondents were for borrowing books, 77.50% for reading newspapers, 68.75% for studying, 46.25% for getting

information from reference books, 36.25% for gathering information. To do this, 31.25% visit the library to refer to journals, 3.75% to prepare research paper, 2.50% to refer to theses.

Table no. 4: Searching for information from the library

S.N.	Searching for information from the library	Respondents	%
1.	by looking through the cupboard	54	67.50
2.	with the help of librarian and library staff	36	45.00
3.	Subject wise bibliography	28	35.00
4.	As per Catalogue Card	17	21.25

Table no. 4, According to when asked the question about the respondents searching for information from the college library, 67.50% of the total respondents search for information from the shelves

themselves, 45% with the help of librarians and library staff, 35% according to the subject-wise bibliography, 21.25% according to the Catalogue card.

Table no. 5: Use of library reading materials

S.N.	Use of reading material in library	Respondents	%
1.	Textbook	72	90.00
2.	Reference book	37	46.25
3.	Periodical	24	30.00
4.	Newspapers	58	72.50
5.	Government publications	07	8.75
6.	Research report	00	00
7.	Bibliography	02	2.50
8.	Thesis	02	2.50
9.	E-publications	05	6.25

Table no. 5, According to when asked about the type of reading materials used by the respondents in the college library, 90% of the total respondents said textbooks, 72.50% newspapers, 46.25%

reference books, 30% periodicals, 8.75% government publications, 6.25% e - Publications, 2.50% visit the library to find bibliography and thesis.

Table no. 6: Searching for information in the library

S.N.	Searching for information in the libraries	Respondents	%
1.	Like the author	43	53.75
2.	According to the Bibliography	66	82.50
3.	According to the publisher	08	10.00
4.	Subject wise	31	38.75
5.	According to the syllabus	52	65.00

Table no. 6, According to when asked about how respondents search for information in college libraries, 82.50% of the total respondents visit the library to

search for information by bibliography, 65% by course, 53.75% by author, 38.75% by subject, and 10% by publisher.

Table no. 7: Purpose of information search

S.N.	Information Seeking Purpose	Respondents	%
1.	For career development	22	27.50
2.	Solving immediate practical problems	34	42.50
3.	To stay updated	59	73.75
4.	To write an article	06	7.50

Table no. 7, According to when asked about the purpose of searching information of the respondents in the college library, 73.75% of the total respondents visit the library to stay up-to-

date, 42.50% to solve immediate practical problems, 27.50% for career development and 7.50% of the respondents visit the library for writing articles.

Table no. 8: Difficulties faced by those who get information from the library

S.N.	Difficulties	Respondents	%
1.	Reading material is not available	08	10.00
2.	Library staff were not ready to serve	06	7.50
3.	Information materials are incomplete	11	13.75
4.	Information scattered across multiple sources	27	33.75
5.	Lack of time	19	23.75
6.	Don't know how to use the catalogue	16	20.00

7.	The information is huge	22	27.50
8.	Lack of knowledge regarding use of library	09	11.25

Table no. 8, According to 8, when asked about the difficulties faced by the respondents in getting information in the college library, 33.75% of the total respondents said information scattered in many sources, 27.50% information is too large, 23.75% lack of time, 20% do not

Conclusion:

Information seeking is a process and information seeking behavior is the expression of a library user during the process of information seeking. It is one of the most widely researched topics in library and information science. Much of the research on information seeking behavior is about the use of library resources by users and their information needs or the purpose of a library visit. They do not analyze or observe the actual information search behavior of users during the information search process, so there is a need to rediscover various research methods in library and informatics in addition to survey that will help to study and analyze the actual information search behavior of users while searching for information. Emphasis on information seeking behavior is important because behavior is always greater than knowledge.

1. 37.50% of the total respondents visit the library daily.
2. 48.75% of the total respondents visit the library for half an hour to one hour.
3. 68.75% of the total respondents were for studying in Library.
4. 67.50% of the total respondents search for information from the shelves themselves.
5. 90% of the total respondents said textbook are reading material use in Library.

know how to use the catalogue, 13.75% information materials are incomplete, 11.25% lack of knowledge about library usage, 10% reading material is not available while 7.50% respondents mentioned library staff not ready to serve.

6. 82.50% of the total respondents visit the library to search for information by bibliography.
7. 73.75% of the total respondents visit the library to stay up-to-date for purpose of information.
8. 33.75% of the total respondents said information scattered in many sources difficulties faced get information from the Library.

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